

User Acceptance and Usability Insights from A Pilot Study of an Integrated Wearable and Contact Tracing App in Nigeria

Bolanle Adefowoke Ojokoh ^a, Tolulope Anthonia Adebayo ^b, Tobore Victor Igbe ^c, Olusola Tope Babalola ^d, and Tunde Tajudeen Yusuf ^e

^{a, b} Department of Information Systems, Federal University of Technology, P.M.B. 704, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

^c Center for Diabetes Technology, Department of Psychiatry & Neurobehavioral Sciences, University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA 22903, USA

^dDepartment of Computer Science, Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Nigeria

^e Department of Mathematics, Federal University of Technology, P.M.B. 704, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

^aCorresponding author: bojokoh@futa.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study presents findings from a pilot evaluation of user experiences with *Tracy*, an integrated contact tracing and health monitoring system comprising an IoT-based wearable device and a mobile application. The wearable tracks physiological indicators (e.g., body temperature, heart rate), while the app facilitates location-based contact tracing and movement analysis. 128 participants from six geopolitical zones used the system over a period of five months and provided feedback on their experiences, including their willingness for continued use. Data preprocessing (cleaning, tokenization and lemmatization), thematic extraction using Latent Dirichlet Allocation, and rule-based sentiment analysis were employed to analyze feedback. Results show strong positive perceptions of Usability (90%) and Engagement/Interest (80%), whereas Performance (14.3%) and Content/Features (9.1%) indicated areas for improvement. The study provides actionable insights for refining digital health tools in resource-conscious settings while balancing functionality with user experience.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis; Digital health technology; Wearable sensors; Contact tracing app; mHealth adoption

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global health landscape has witnessed a significant transformation driven by advancements in digital health tools, particularly mobile health (mHealth) applications and wearable devices (Carey et al. 2016). These technologies have proven crucial in enabling real-time health monitoring, early detection of infectious diseases, and improving communication between

individuals and health authorities (Ojokoh et al., 2022). The rapid global deployment of mobile contact tracing apps during the COVID-19 pandemic represented a landmark moment in digital public health, offering a potential technological solution to curb disease transmission (Ferretti et al., 2020; Whitelaw et al., 2020). Integrated systems that combine physiological sensing with geolocation-based monitoring have also emerged as promising tools for epidemic preparedness and response (Specht et al., 2025). Despite the effectiveness of integrated digital health systems, their success depends largely on user acceptance and usability, two critical dimensions that influence sustained engagement. Poorly designed or culturally mismatched tools often suffer from low uptake and abandonment, rendering them ineffective in real-world applications (Leung et al., 2024).

In response, this study introduces *Tracy*, an integrated digital health system combining an IoT-based wearable device and a mobile application for contact tracing. The wearable monitors physiological metrics such as body temperature and heart rate, while the mobile app facilitates geospatial tracing and movement analysis. The system was piloted in Nigeria and obtained responses about the end users' experience. Analyzing user feedback presents an opportunity to understand experiential factors for contact tracing. Existing approaches often rely on black-box machine learning models that lack transparency for public health stakeholders (Rödseth et al., 2023). Recent work in natural language processing has demonstrated the value of combining topic modeling with sentiment analysis for health app evaluation (Hussein et al., 2023; Lau et al., 2022), but few studies have applied these methods to contact tracing apps specifically. Moreover, the field lacks standardized frameworks that balance computational efficiency with interpretability, particularly for moderate-sized datasets where complex deep learning approaches may be unnecessary or impractical (Klein et al., 2021). This gap is significant because public health agencies and app developers need clear, actionable insights, not just statistical patterns, to iteratively improve digital tools. This study addresses these limitations by developing and applying a three-stage analytical framework to user feedback from the *Tracy* contact tracing app. Additionally, it identifies both strengths and limitations of the system in its current form to provide actionable insights for improving the system before broader deployment and longer-term testing.

METHODOLOGY

This section explains the steps taken from preprocessing to analysis to reveal users' behaviour towards the app. Figure 1 describes the systematic approach for analysing the obtained comments.

Figure 1: A description of three stages of systematic analysis of comments from users of the contact tracing app

Data Collection

The comments were gathered from an In-app feedback form from participants from the six geopolitical zones, saved in the database and exported as a single Excel file for further processing.

Data Preprocessing

This stage involved removing or obscuring personally identifiable information from data to protect individuals' privacy. The source file was read and the comment column was renamed to a variable name to identify the column. Further, duplicates, spam, and irrelevant comments, were removed. The text was normalised with nltk.stem Python Library to ensure all the comments are consistent and remove unwanted characters. Lastly, tokenization and lemmatization/stemming were carried out using NLP and part-of-speech tagging tools.

Theme Creation

We employed Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), an unsupervised natural language processing technique to identify dominant themes in the dataset. The tokenised text was used to generate a dictionary and a bag-of-words corpus, which served as input for the LDA model. The model was trained using the Gensim library, with the number of topics empirically set to n , balancing interpretability and model coherence. Each topic was represented by a distribution of keywords, which were manually interpreted and labelled based on the most representative terms. For instance, a topic containing terms such as “easy,” “navigation,” and “interface” was labelled as the “Ease of Use” theme.

Thematic Analysis

Each cleaned comment was analysed against a predefined set of keywords associated with key themes. If any keyword from a theme's list was present in a comment, the comment was assigned to that theme. If a comment matched keywords from multiple themes, the first matching theme in the priority list was assigned. Comments that did not match any of the specified keyword sets were labelled as "Other".

Sentiment Analysis

To quantify users’ emotional responses to the app, we utilised the TextBlob library in Python to generate a polarity score ranging from -1.0 to 1.0. Values closer to -1.0 indicate strong negative sentiment, values near 0.0 suggest neutrality, and values approaching 1.0 reflect strong positive sentiment. Based on these scores, comments were categorised into three sentiment classes: Positive, Neutral, and Negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis and evaluation are presented in this section, as well as a data description of the collected users’ responses.

Data Description

The data comprises one response from 128 participants, well-structured with four main columns, each entry capturing the timestamp, email address, expression of the user’s overall experience (feedback), and whether the participant is willing to join similar research in the future. After preprocessing, the number of records was 127 responses.

Theme Analysis

Four themes (Usability, performance, content/feature and engagement/interest) were derived from the LDA model, where the number of topics, n , was set at 10 to extract topics to determine the themes. Table 1 presents the themes and the keywords that describe each theme. The Usability theme assesses how easily users interact with the app; the performance theme refers to the technical reliability and responsiveness of the app. Content/Features theme relates to the tools, modules and design elements. The engagement/Interest theme reflects how captivating and meaningful the experience is for users.

Table 1: Keywords that describe the themes for analysing users’ comments

Theme	Theme Keywords
Usability	navigate, easy, simple, straightforward, intuitive, friendly, seamless, smooth, direct, interface, accessible, clear, effortless, efficient, convenient, fast, onboard
Performance	lag, bug, fast, response, slow, laggy, buggy, crash, stable, error, loading, freeze, frozen, glitchy, efficient, optimised, perform
Content / Features	access, feature, tool, option, function, content, module, layout, dashboard, custom, interact, accessible, update, integrate, control, search
Engagement / Interest	learn, engage, interest, enjoy, fun, entertain, immerse, interact, addictive, help, reward, excite, motivate, stimulate, educate, inform

Figures 2 and 3 are two bar charts that present a comparison of how user comments were distributed across thematic categories when assigned to a single theme versus when allowed to be classified under multiple themes. In Figure 2, 52.8%, fell into the “Others” category, suggesting that many responses either were too general for precise categorisation or addressed areas outside the predefined themes. The remaining comments were more evenly distributed across the defined themes, with the Content/Features theme receiving 17.6%, Usability theme, with 16.0%. The Engagement/Interest theme is 8.0%, and the Performance theme is the least represented with only 5.6%, reflecting fewer remarks on user interaction and system efficiency. In contrast, Figure 3, based on multiple-theme assignments, captures a more nuanced view of the feedback. While the “Others” category still dominates with 52.8%, the number of mentions for the Content/Features theme rose to 25.6%, and the Engagement/Interest theme nearly tripled to 23.2%. The Usability theme remains constant at 16.0%, while the Performance theme increases slightly to 7.2%. This

broader classification approach reveals that many comments addressed more than one theme, particularly around features and user engagement. The comparison highlights that multi-theme tagging better captures the multidimensional nature of user feedback, offering a richer, more accurate understanding of user experience concerns. Table 2 shows some examples of users' comments that are grouped into the corresponding theme. The table also describes the output of the preprocessed comments, which include removing stop words, converting text to lowercase, removing punctuation, special characters, stop words and lemmatisation.

Figure 2: Distribution of comments across thematic categories when assigned to a single-theme

Figure 3: Distribution of comments across thematic categories when assigned to multiple themes

Table 2: Examples of User Feedback Before and After Preprocessing, Categorized by Theme

	Comment after preprocessing	Theme
It was awesome, and easy to know the mobility of people	awesome easy know mobility people	Usability

Noticed even while the app was showing "Tracy is running in the background" it still doesn't affect the performance of the phone.	notice even app show tracy run background still doesnt affect performance phone	Performance
Indeed a great method of exercise a research process, em the only experiences I had is I didn't notice how my data where been taken but I believe that it wasn't having any negative impact on my phone	Indeed great method exercise research process em experience didn't notice data take believe wasn't negative impact phone	Content / Features
It provides more information concerning invisible germs than can be harmful to humans.	provide information concern invisible germ harmful human	Engagement / Interest
It was good so far	good so far	Others

A further thematic analysis of the comments initially categorized as 'Others' (52.8% of the total) involved open coding to identify recurrent topics, which were grouped into two primary themes: General Sentiment and Participation Experience. The results showed that 54.4% of these comments expressed a General Sentiment, such as "It was nice," "It was good so far," and "It was awesome." In contrast, the remaining 45.6% constituted the Participation Experience theme, which captured reflections on the user's role in the study, from positive endorsements like "It was an amazing experience and also stress-free" to criticisms regarding usability, such as "The app wasn't responsive and I hate could understand its working pattern."

Thematic Sentiment Analysis

Figure 4 describes the distribution of positive, negative, and neutral sentiments for each theme. The sentiment analysis results highlight a notably positive perception of the usability of the app, with 90% of users expressing favourable views. Very few users reported negative experiences (5%), indicating minimal frustration with the user interface or workflow. Similarly, the engagement/interest theme yielded strong results, with 80% positive sentiment and no negative feedback at all. This implies the app was enjoyable and meaningful for users. Neutral feedback in this area (20%) might reflect users who were engaged but not particularly enthusiastic or expressive in their comments. Regarding the content/feature theme, 72.7% of feedback was positive. However, the 9.1% negative sentiment and a relatively high neutral rate (18.2%) may point to areas where content could be expanded, refined, or made more accessible. For the performance theme, sentiment was less favourable compared to other categories: while 71.4% was positive, indicating general satisfaction with speed and reliability, 14.3% of users expressed dissatisfaction. The remaining neutral feedback could suggest that some users did not focus on or experience notable performance issues. Overall, while sentiment is largely positive across all dimensions, performance and content/feature represent areas with more room for enhancement.

Figure 4: Distribution of sentiment classifications (positive, negative, and neutral) across the thematic categories: [A] Usability, [B] Content/Features, [C] Engagement/Interest, [D] Performance, and [E] Others.

Figure 5 describes the distribution of users’ responses regarding their willingness to participate in similar future research, categorised by thematic areas, revealing overwhelmingly positive engagement across all themes. Users who commented on Content/Features and Engagement/Interest showed 100% affirmative responses, indicating strong enthusiasm and a high level of satisfaction with the app’s functionalities and its ability to capture their interest. Similarly, Usability also had a very high rate of positive responses, with 95% indicating ‘Yes’, and only 5% responding with ‘Maybe’, suggesting that users who found the app easy and intuitive to use were also highly inclined to participate in future research.

In contrast, slightly lower levels of commitment were observed among those whose comments focused on “Performance” and “Others” themes. For Performance, 85.7% of users responded ‘Yes’, while 14.3% expressed uncertainty (Maybe), likely reflecting concerns about technical reliability, such as glitches. Similarly, in the Others category, which includes feedback not directly tied to the main usability themes, 81.8% responded positively, while 18.2% chose ‘Maybe’, possibly due to more mixed or ambiguous user experiences. Overall, the data indicate that users who had clear, positive experiences, especially in terms of features and engagement, were the most likely to express interest in future participation, whereas those who mentioned broader or technical concerns showed slightly more hesitation.

Figure 5: Distribution of users' responses based on their interest in participating in similar research in the future, categorised by the following themes: [A] Usability, [B] Content/Features, [C] Engagement/Interest, [D] Performance, and [E] Others

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study demonstrates the value of applying a structured, data-driven approach to understanding user feedback on a contact tracing app. By integrating thematic analysis with sentiment assessment, we were able to extract meaningful insights about users' experiences, preferences, and challenges. The findings revealed that while users generally responded positively to the app's usability and engagement features, issues related to performance and content refinement still pose barriers to broader adoption and long-term use. To increase the adoption and effectiveness of the contact tracing app, several strategic actions are recommended. First, addressing technical issues, such as improving app stability and optimising performance, should be prioritised to build and maintain user trust. Second, expanding and refining app features in response to user feedback, including adding new tools or enhancing personalisation, can make the app more useful and appealing. Third, given the high levels of user engagement, the app presents a strong opportunity to incorporate public health education and behaviour change messaging to further its impact. Additionally, outreach efforts should also be targeted toward user segments reporting positive experiences, emphasising usability, utility, and the app's contribution to public health to encourage uptake and continued use. Finally, the feedback analysis approach developed in this study should

be institutionalised as part of a real-time monitoring system, allowing for agile responses to user concerns and ensuring that the app evolves alongside user needs and expectations.

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